

MASTERY, CHALLENGES, AND OPPORTUNITIES OF TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION TEACHERS ABOUT PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR THE ENHANCED CAPABILITY BUILDING PROGRAM

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Mastery, Challenges, and Opportunities of Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers in Relation to Performance: Basis for the Enhanced Capability Building Program

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Abstract

The study determined the mastery, challenges, and opportunities of TLE teachers in relation to performance: basis for the enhancement of training programs. There were 107 Grade 9 and 10 TLE teachers in the Division of Bago City for School Year 2023-2024. They were taken as subject and respondents of the study. The research instruments of this study were a researcher-made to measure the level of mastery of TLE teachers, their challenges and opportunities encountered. It was validated by five experts in the field of education and it underwent reliability testing. Frequency, percent distribution, mean, T test, ANOVA, and Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation were the statistical tools used to analyze the data. The result shows that most of the respondents were female, were in the age range of 31- 40 years old, teaching for 16 years and above, married, and in Bachelor's degree. The TLE teachers were on the level of near mastery, have a moderate level of challenges encountered in teaching, have low level of opportunities, and with outstanding performance. There are significant differences in the mastery of TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their age and highest educational attainment. A significant differences in the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their age and highest educational attainment were also noted. Furthermore, there are significant differences in the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their age, length of service, and highest educational attainment. A significant relationships were noted between the mastery of TLE teachers and their performance, between the level of challenges encountered and their performance, and between opportunities obtained by TLE teachers and their performance.

Keywords: *program, performance, teachers, Technology and Livelihood Education*

Introduction

Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) stands as a fundamental component within the educational framework of the Philippines, covering a spectrum of practical skills drawn from Home Economics, Information and Communication Technology, Agri-Fishery, and Industrial Arts. It equips students with foundational knowledge, essential skills, as well as a positive work ethic and attitude (Teachers Collegesj, 2019). TLE plays a crucial role in preparing individuals to be productive contributors to the contemporary workforce. Opting for a career path and acquiring the relevant technological and livelihood competencies associated with that chosen field or industry can significantly enhance prospects for success in one's professional endeavors (Ssemugenyi, 2023).

TLE underscores the importance of thoroughly mastering each life skill outlined within its framework through practical application (Darsih, 2018). Consequently, TLE entails a multifaceted process that transcends traditional classroom boundaries and extends into real-world scenarios. TLE educators shoulder a significant responsibility in readying students for the professional realm by imparting industry-specific competencies and knowledge. Nonetheless, ensuring the effective acquisition of knowledge and skills, alongside delivering engaging practical learning opportunities, presents considerable challenges (Barcelona et al., 2023).

Teaching Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) can be challenging for educators when they lack access to updated equipment and adequate resources. Continuous training is crucial, especially in dynamic fields like technology and vocational education, to keep up with the latest advancements. Due to limited budgets, some TLE programs must rely on specific facilities and tools, such as workshops or laboratories. However, insufficient infrastructure may hinder the successful execution of educational activities, particularly those involving hands-on learning experiences (Garcia, 2024). Bawar (2019) highlighted the significance of sufficient instructional facilities, equipment, and materials in cultivating a stronger enthusiasm for TLE among students and educators alike. The presence of these resources not only enhances academic performance but also depends heavily on the attitudes, interests, and motivations of both parties. Consequently, the lack of essential resources frequently results in an inability to meet the necessary competencies, ultimately affecting academic success.

Blanca (2019) emphasized the crucial role of teaching strategies in enhancing student performance, highlighting how the selection and implementation of these strategies significantly influence students' attitudes and academic outcomes. Such challenges pose significant hurdles not just for students but also for educators. TLE teachers are tasked with transforming these challenges into opportunities for meaningful educational advancement. However, there is a limited body of research addressing the specific challenges and opportunities faced by TLE teachers (Alonzo et al., 2023).

Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers in the Division of Bago face several challenges impacting their teaching and students' educational experiences. One of the main problems is the absence of modern tools and resources essential for assisting students in developing practical skills. This shortfall lowers the standard of instruction in the TLE program also because of the limited

opportunities for professional training, which prevents them from adopting modern teaching methods and integrating new technologies into their lessons. These challenges can lower teacher motivation and mastery and make it difficult for students to develop their skills. Therefore, this study aims to explore in greater depth of the level of mastery, challenges, and opportunities encountered by TLE teachers in relation to academic performance as basis for the enhanced capability building program.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of mastery, challenges, and opportunities of TLE teachers in relation to their performance in the Division of Bago City as basis for the enhanced capability building program for School Year 2024-2025. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the TLE teachers when taken in terms of?
 - 1.1. sex
 - 1.2. age
 - 1.3. Length of service
 - 1.4. Marital status
 - 1.5. Highest educational attainment
2. What is the mastery level of TLE teachers?
3. What is the level of challenges encountered by TLE teachers?
4. What is the level of opportunities obtained by TLE teachers?
5. What is the level of teacher's performance?
6. Is there a significant difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when taken in terms of their profile?
7. Is there a significant difference in the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when taken in terms of their profile?
8. Is there a significant difference in the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when taken in terms of their profile?
9. Is there a significant relationship between the mastery of TLE teachers and their performance?
10. Is there a significant relationship between the challenges encountered by TLE teachers and their performance?
11. Is there a significant relationship between the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers and their performance?
12. What enhanced capability building program can be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive-correlational research design to determine the mastery level, challenges encountered and the opportunities of the TLE teachers in relation to teacher's performance in the Schools Division of Bago City. According to Sharma (2019), a descriptive quantitative research design is a systematic approach utilized to collect, analyze, and interpret numerical data, aiming to describe and summarize the characteristics, behavior, or aspects within a specific population or sample. A correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them. This study combines two research strategies-descriptive design and correlational research – into a quantitative descriptive correlational research design. Observing and objectively characterizing individual behavior in connection to situational circumstances is the goal of descriptive design.

Respondents

The subject and respondents of this study were the TLE teachers in the Division of Bago City for school year 2023-2024. They were chosen as respondents of the study since they are handling the same group of students from the first to the fourth quarter of the school year.

Instrument

The research instruments of this study were a researcher-made questionnaire to measure the level of mastery of TLE teachers, their challenges and opportunities encountered. Part 1 of the questionnaire determined the profile of TLE teachers as to their sex, age, length of service, marital status, highest educational attainment. Part 2 was a 30 item test to measure the mastery level of TLE teachers in the subject. It is a researcher-made questionnaire patterned from MCQs and Answers (2024). Part 3 was composed of 15 items to measure the challenges encountered by TLE teachers and is answerable by strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree or disagree, agree, and strongly agree. Lastly, Part 4 of the survey instrument measured the opportunities of TLE teachers which is composed of 15 items and was responded by choosing one of the five likert-type responses: answerable by always, often, sometimes, rarely and never. The construction of the statements was based on the available instruments in the literature about challenges and opportunities encountered by TLE teachers. However, the researcher also construct statements that are based on the experiences of the target respondents.

Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, permission from the Schools Division Superintendent and principals of Junior High School in the Division of Bago City to allow the researcher administer the survey questionnaire to the Grade 9 and 10 TLE teachers (see Appendix

B.1). After the approval was obtained, the validated and reliability tested researcher-made instruments were administered to the respondents. To determine the teacher's performance, the researcher asked the data from TLE teachers, their IPCRF rating for SY 2023-2024. After these procedures, data were tallied, analyzed, and presented according to the problems posed in the study using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Data Analysis

To analyze the data gathered, the following descriptive and inferential statistics were employed.

For Problem number 1, which determined the profile of the TLE teachers when taken in terms of sex, age, length of service, marital status, highest educational attainment, frequency and percent distribution were used.

For Problem number 2, which determined the mastery level of TLE teachers, mean was used.

For Problem number 3, which determined the challenges encountered by the TLE teachers, mean was used.

For Problem number 4, which determined the opportunities for TLE teachers, mean was used.

For Problem number 5, which determined the teacher's performance, mean was used.

For Problem number 6, which determined if there is a significant difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when taken in terms of their profile, T test and ANOVA were used.

For Problem number 7, which determined if there is a significant difference in the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when taken in terms of their profile, T test and ANOVA were used.

For Problem number 8, which determined if there is a significant difference in the opportunities of TLE teachers when taken in terms of their profile, T test and ANOVA were used.

For Problem number 9, which determined if there is a significant relationship between the mastery of TLE teachers and teaching performance, Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used.

For Problem number 10, which determined if there is a significant relationship between the challenges encountered by TLE teachers and the teacher's performance, Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used.

For Problem number 11, which determined if there is a significant relationship between the opportunities of TLE teachers and the teacher's performance, Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and explains the gathered data. To address the problem statement, the data are carefully organized using the relevant statistical tools.

Profile of TLE Teachers

The table below shows the profile of TLE teachers.

Table 1. Frequency and Percent Distribution of TLE Teachers in Bago City Division according to Profile

Profile	Category	f	%
Sex	Male	35	32.71
	Female	72	67.29
	Total	107	100.00
Age	30 years old & below	16	14.95
	31-40 years old	45	42.06
	41-50 years old	36	33.64
	51-60 years old	10	9.35
	60 years old and above	0	0.00
	Total	107	100.00
Length of Service	1-5 years	12	11.21
	6-10 years	25	23.36
	11-15 years	34	31.78
	16 years and above	36	33.64
	Total	107	100.00
Marital Status	Single	28	26.17
	Married	79	73.83
	Total	107	100.00

Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's degree	49	45.79
	Master's degree	52	48.60
	Doctorate degree	6	5.61
	Total	107	100.00

Based on Table 1, majority of the respondents were female with a frequency of 72 or 67.29 percent of the 107 respondents. On the other hand, male is composed of 35 or 32.71 percent.

As to age, most of them are in the age range of 31- 40 years old with a frequency of 45 or 42.06 percent. Thirty-six or 33.64 percent of the respondents are in the age group of 41-50 years old, 16 or 14.95 percent are 30 years old and below, and 10 or 9.35 percent are 51-60 years old.

As to length of service, most of the respondents were teaching 16 years and above with a frequency of 36 or 33.64 percent, 11-15 years with 34 or 31.78 percent, 6-10 years with a frequency of 25 or 23.36 percent, and those who are teaching 1-5 years with 12 or 11.21 percent of the total respondents.

Marital status showed that majority of the respondents are married with a frequency of 79 or 73.83 percent while 28 or 26.17 percent of the respondents are single.

In terms of their highest educational attainment, majority of the respondents are in Bachelor's degree with a frequency of 52 or 48.60 percent followed by those who have with bachelor's degree with a frequency of 49 or 45.79 percent with 41 or 29.30 percent, and with Doctorate degree with six or 5.61 percent, with a total of 107 respondents.

Level of Mastery of TLE Teachers

The table on the next page shows the level of mastery of TLE teachers.

Table 2. *Level of Mastery of TLE Teachers*

<i>Mastery Level of Teachers</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Exceeds Mastery	0	20.82	Near Mastery
Mastery	31		
Near Mastery	40		
Below Mastery	28		
No Evidence	8		
Total	107		

Table 2 shows that out of 107 respondents, there are 31 who are in the mastery level, 40 are in the near mastery, 28 are below mastery, and 8 have no evidence of mastery. As a whole, the mean score is 20.82 which is interpreted as near mastery.

This reflects that the respondents possess average skill in the subject TLE. They have an average knowledge in the subject. This implies that TLE teachers need to enhance their knowledge in the subject taught to provide in-depth explanations or answer advanced questions and increase confidence in their teaching abilities. Teachers have considerable subject-matter knowledge and expertise, which could assist students meet learning goals and become more involved in the learning process. When a teacher skillfully teaches lessons to pupils, their competence establishes them as a knowledgeable authority and promotes fulfillment in their teaching attempts.

This finding does not confirm to the study of Zabala (2018) that the TLE teachers show a satisfactory level of competency across all areas outlined in the NCBTS. This indicates that they possess adequate knowledge, skills, and attitudes related to their teaching subjects. The findings suggest that the teachers feel confident in their abilities to effectively teach and transfer skills to their students, as indicated by their responses to the questionnaire and self-reflection. It was noted that when teachers successfully impart skills to their students through their performances, it also reflects their proficiency in knowledge and attitude towards teaching. Additionally, teachers have demonstrated effective management of available school resources.

Disagreeing with the results, the study of Basal (2022) on the instructional competencies of TLE (Technology and Livelihood Education) teachers, focusing on their mastery of the subject matter. Teachers self-assessed their competencies as competent, yielding a grand mean of 4.09. This indicates that teachers possess substantial knowledge and skills pertaining to the subject matter, potentially facilitating the achievement of learning objectives and fostering student engagement. Such expertise positions the teacher as a knowledgeable authority, fostering satisfaction in their teaching endeavors when they effectively deliver lessons to students.

Villegas (2022) shared the different results. According to him, the students believe their TLE teachers have a high level of mastery of the subject matter. The students also believe that their teachers are able to adapt their teaching techniques in an appropriate, effective, and systematic manner. This suggests that the teachers' competence and teaching methods are highly valued by the students and may contribute to their outstanding work skills.

Calanog (2021) also have a contrasting result. According to him, TLE teachers demonstrated a high level of competence in their knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas. They were particularly skilled in motivating learners to establish

links between different topics, which was the area where they received the highest ratings. The teachers were also highly competent in encouraging students to express their thoughts and ideas in a clear and effective manner. Furthermore, the analysis revealed that the teachers were very adept at integrating ICT into their teaching methods to enhance student learning.

Level of Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers

The table below shows the level of challenges encountered by TLE teachers.

Table 3. Level of Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers

<i>Level of Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Very High	1	3.08	Moderate
High	19		
Moderate	76		
Low	11		
Very Low	0		
Total	107		

Based on Table 3, there is one respondent who has a very high level of challenges encountered in teaching, 19 have high, 76 have moderate, and 11 have low level of challenges. As a whole, their mean score is 3.08 which indicates that they have a moderate level of challenges encountered in teaching.

The result implies that teachers have a moderate level of difficulties and obstacles encountered in the teaching practice. They have encountered challenges in their learning resources, textbooks/learning materials to deliver the lesson, they do not have stable internet connection to properly integrate lessons specifically in ICT, the tools and equipment not that enough to cater the number of learners in the area of their specialization, textbooks/learning materials are not enough for all the learners, have extra paper works to do, sometimes they spend their personal money to meet the competencies in the area of specialization assigned to them, and they lack various teaching strategies in delivering their lesson.

Beinert et al. (2021) agrees in the findings that TLE teachers often find a disparity between the curriculum guidelines and how they actually teach. When conducting face-to-face classes, TLE instructors stress the importance of food nutrition and the limited time allotted for student activities, yet there exists a disconnect between the perspectives of teachers and students. To address these issues and align teaching practices with curriculum requirements, a greater emphasis should be placed on a comprehensive approach to nutrition education.

Additionally, Barcelona et al. (2023) agree to this findings when they state that the theme of challenges in teaching Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) covers a range of issues, including problems related to people, teaching methods, and resources. Human-related issues often involve things like not having enough well-trained teachers, having too many students for each teacher, or dealing with student motivation problems. These problems can make it hard for TLE teaching to work well. Pedagogical problems are about teaching methods and strategies. Teachers might struggle to include hands-on activities, use new teaching methods, or adapt to the different ways students learn. Material problems are about not having enough teaching resources and facilities. For example, not having modern equipment or enough teaching materials can limit the chance for hands-on learning, which is really important in TLE. These three areas—human, pedagogical, and material—create challenges for teachers trying to give high-quality, interesting, and effective TLE lessons.

With similar findings, Zabala (2018) also stated that the weaknesses found in TLE teachers include their struggle with using technology for teaching, not setting clear learning objectives suitable for students, lacking creative lesson plans, and failing to create a learning atmosphere that meets community needs and encourages focused learning.

The results also coincide with the result of Villacorta and Arnado's (2023) study when they found that TLE teachers face additional obstacles such as limited access to updated equipment and materials for hands-on activities, which hinders effective teaching and learning. Moreover, they often experience difficulties in keeping up with advancements in technology and industry standards due to limited opportunities for professional development. These challenges contribute to the overall complexity of their roles and highlight the need for comprehensive support systems to enhance their effectiveness in delivering quality technical education.

Furthermore, Tiyanes and Ponsades (2024) also agree to the findings of this study when they present that one of the realities in teaching that is faced by many, not just only the technical education graduates, is to teach subjects unrelated to their expertise. The difficulty of teaching subjects that might not be relevant to their area of expertise is one issue that concerns of teachers. Teachers in technical fields have a tendency to teach a wide range of subjects that may fall beyond the scope of their particular expertise or experience. This can present challenges for the teachers since they may not have the same degree of competency or confidence in these seemingly unrelated subjects.

Level of Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers

The table below shows the level of opportunities obtained by TLE teachers.

Table 4. *Level of Opportunities Obtained by f TLE Teachers*

<i>Level of Opportunities of the TLE Teachers</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Very High	0	2.65	Low
High	3		
Moderate	57		
Low	42		
Very Low	5		
Total	107		

The table highlights that there are three TLE teachers who claim a high level of opportunities obtained, 57 have moderate, 42 have low, and five have obtained a very low level of opportunities. Overall, the mean is 2.65 which is interpreted as low level of opportunities obtained by the TLE teachers.

This finding implies that the TLE teachers have a low level of opportunity to access resources that could aid in enhancing their teaching techniques. They have a low opportunity to be invited as resource speaker to share their knowledge and skills in their area of specialization, and low opportunity to apply the skills they have as TLE teachers outside the school like at home and community. They also have a low opportunity to enhance their teaching techniques or addressing obstacles in their professional roles.

The results align with the study of Barcelona et al. (2022) which discusses the significance of Vocational Skills Competency Training in the realm of TLE instruction. They highlight how TLE offers teachers a valuable opportunity to focus on practical, hands-on learning and vocational expertise. By emphasizing these aspects, TLE enables teachers to equip students with skills directly relevant to various professional fields. Consequently, teachers not only help students grasp academic concepts but also show them how these concepts apply in real-world scenarios, which often enhances understanding and engagement. This approach allows teachers to go beyond traditional teaching methods, exposing students to vocational training that can shape their career paths. Moreover, the hands-on nature of TLE encourages teachers to continually learn and adapt, improving their teaching methods and technical skills over time. Ultimately, through TLE, teachers play a pivotal role in preparing students to become skilled and productive workers, thereby contributing to the nation's workforce development.

Level of Teacher's Performance

The table below shows the level of teacher's performance.

Table 5. *Level of Teacher's Performance*

<i>Level of Performance</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Outstanding	87	4.57	Outstanding
Very Satisfactory	20		
Satisfactory	0		
Unsatisfactory	0		
Poor	0		
Total	107		

In Table 5, the mean score of 107 teachers is 4.57 which is interpreted as outstanding. There are 87 teachers who have an outstanding performance, and 20 have a very satisfactory teaching performance.

The findings implies that the TLE teachers have the ability to accomplish their roles as educators and have the capacity to deliver what is expected from them. This also means that they have an extraordinary level of achievement and commitment. TLE teachers display an exceptional job mastery in all areas of responsibility, contributing to the organization with marked excellence.

The finding drawn from this study is similar to those of Erojo (2020) who also reported satisfactory academic performance among the 41 feeding recipients, with an average score of 84.4. This suggests that the beneficiaries are capable of competing and excelling academically, despite having received fewer nutrients compared to their peers with normal nutritional status.

Difference in the Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Sex

The table below shows the difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when grouped according to their sex.

Table 6.1. *Difference in the Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Male	35	20.46
Female	72	21.00

Computed value (t): -0.65

p-value: 0.871

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that using T-test, results reveal that the p-value of 0.871 is higher than the 0.05 level of significance with a computed value of -0.65; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their sex.

This result implies that the mastery of TLE teachers are the same when they are grouped according to their sex. This further suggest that they acquired mastery in TLE irrespective of their sex. They were provided with equal opportunities for advancement and improve regardless of gender. They have inclusive and supportive teaching environment where all teachers, regardless of gender, can thrive and excel.

However, previous research denotes that gender has been identified as a key factor influencing competence levels. Sánchez Prieto et al. (2020) highlighted the underrepresentation of females in vocational education, despite the majority of teachers in this field being women. The study also reveals that females, particularly those in vocational education, display a high degree of competence. This finding suggests that, although they are underrepresented, female teachers excel in their roles, demonstrating notable proficiency and expertise.

Difference in the Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age

The table below shows the difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when grouped according to their age.

Table 6.2. *Difference in the Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age*

Age	n	Mean
30 years old & below	16	18.56
31-40 years old	45	20.78
41-50 years old	36	22.11
51-60 years old	10	20.00

Computed value (F): 3.23
p-value: 0.025
Decision: Reject Ho
Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Results of ANOVA show that the mean of the mastery level of TLE teachers aging 30 years old & below is 18.56, those who are 31-40 years old is 20.78, the 41-50 years old have a mean of 22.11, and those who are 51-60 years old have a mean of 20.00. ITs computed value is 3.23 and the p-value of 0.025 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when grouped according to their age.

This implies that TLE teachers have different mastery level of the subject they taught when they are grouped according to their age. The level of subject matter expertise varies significantly among different age groups. Older teachers might have more years of teaching experience, extensive practical knowledge, and opportunities for professional development, leading to greater subject mastery. Conversely, younger teachers might be more recently trained in the latest techniques and technologies, but with less practical experience.

Comparison Between Means of Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age

The table below shows the comparison between means of the mastery of TLE teachers when grouped according to their age.

Table 6.3. *Comparison Between Means of Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age*

Comparison	Computed value	p-value	Interpretation
30 years old & below vs. 31-40 years old	-2.22	0.291	Not significant
30 years old & below vs. 51-60 years old	-3.55	0.032	Significant
30 years old & below vs. 41-50 years old	-1.44	0.842	Not significant
31-40 years old vs. 41-50 years old	-1.33	0.511	Not significant
31-40 years old vs. 51-60 years old	0.78	0.955	Not significant
41-50 years old vs. 51-60 years old	2.11	0.519	Not significant

As shown in the table, using Scheffe's test, the computed value of -3.55 and the p-value of 0.032 when the 30 years old & below and 51-60 years old was compared indicates that there is a significant difference at .05 level of significance.

The table also shows that when the teachers who are 30 years old & below and 31-40 years old are compared, the 30 years old & below and 41-50 years old, 31-40 years old and 41-50 years old, 31-40 years old and 51-60 years old, and the 41-50 years old vs. 51-60 years old are compared, there are no significant differences as indicated in the computed values of -2.22, -1.44, -1.33, 0.78, and 2.11, respectively with the p-values of 0.291, 0.842, 0.511, 0.955, and 0.519.

The result of the data above implies that the mastery level of TLE teacher aging 51-60 years old is significantly higher than a teacher who is 30 years old & below. Older teachers in the 51-60 age group often have many more years of teaching experience. Their extensive experience allows them to refine their teaching methods and deepen their subject matter expertise, leading to higher mastery levels.

Over the course of their careers, older teachers likely have had more opportunities for professional development, such as attending workshops, seminars, and advanced training.

This findings was in contradiction to the study of Elli and Ricafort (2020) which assess the competencies of Grade VI Technology and Livelihood education (TLE) teachers. The findings revealed no significant relationship between teachers' age and competency levels in the four TLE areas. Their result suggests that age does not influence TLE teachers' competency in teaching the subject. Similarly, the data indicate that the age of ICT coordinators has little to no impact on their competency across the four domains: technology operations and concepts, social and ethical responsibility, pedagogy, and professionalism. These results imply that TLE and ICT coordinators demonstrate similar competency levels regardless of age

Difference in the Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Length of Service

The table below shows the difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when grouped according to their length of service.

Table 6.4. *Difference in the Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Length of Service*

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1-5 years	12	18.17
6-10 years	25	20.92
11-15 years	34	20.62
16 years and above	36	21.83

Computed value (F): 2.64

p-value: 0.053

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the ANOVA, the table shows that the mean of the mastery level of TLE teachers having rendered service for 1-5 years have a mean of 18.17, those who served for 6-10 years have a mean of 20.92, the mean of those who are 11-15 years in service is 20.62, and those who are 16 years and above have a mean of 21.83

Results of ANOVA also shows that the computed value is 2.64 and the p-value of 0.053 is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when grouped according to their length of service.

This implies that TLE teachers have the same mastery level when they grouped according to their length of service. It means that the level of expertise and knowledge of the subject matter is consistent across teachers, whether they are new to the profession or have many years of experience. It also imply that ongoing professional development and in-service training are equally accessible and effective for both new and experienced teachers, helping to maintain a consistent level of mastery.

This findings is in disagreement with the study of Involvement in Student Achievement by Gonzales-DeHass et al. (2005) as cited by Villacorta & Arnado (2023) where they argued that a teacher's profile significantly impacts their competency levels in the TVL track. Research indicates that the number of years spent in a teaching position strongly predicts competence levels ($\beta = .378, p < .001$). This duration in the role enables teachers to acquire new skills and enhances their self-efficacy. This finding further implies that as teachers accumulate more years of teaching experience, their competencies likewise grow. The cumulative knowledge and skills gained over time contribute to improved teaching competence.

Difference in the Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Marital Status

The table below shows the difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when grouped according to their marital status.

Table 6.5. *Difference in the Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Marital Status*

<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Single	28	19.75
Married	79	21.20

Computed value (t): -1.65

p-value: 0.891

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

As shown in the table, it shows that the mean of the mastery level of single TLE teachers is 19.75 while the male teachers have a mean of 21.20.

Using the ANOVA, the table shows that the computed value is -1.65 and the p-value of 0.891 is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when grouped according to their marital status.

This implies the level of subject matter expertise is similar across teachers regardless of whether they are single or married. Single teachers are equally skilled and knowledgeable in their teaching area as married teachers. The findings also indicate that marital status

does not influence a teacher's ability to master the subject matter in TLE. Personal life circumstances related to marital status have no bearing on professional competence.

This findings was further supported with the study by Elli and Ricafort (2020) where they argued the study revealed no significant relationship between marital status and the competency levels of teachers across the four areas of TLE. This indicates that marital status does not affect a teacher's ability to teach the subject effectively. This finding could be attributed to the role of teachers as generalists, who are primarily responsible for imparting foundational knowledge and skills to their students, regardless of their circumstances

Difference in the Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment

The table on the next page shows the difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

Table 6.6. *Difference in the Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment*

Highest Educational Attainment	n	Mean
Bachelor's degree	49	19.39
Master's degree	52	21.65
Doctorate degree	6	25.33

Computed value (F): 9.19
 p-value: <0.001
 Decision: Reject Ho
 Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 6.6 shows that the mean of the mastery level of TLE teachers having Bachelor’s Degree is 19.39, those with Master's degree have a mean of 21.65, and those with Doctorate degree have a mean of 25.33.

Using the ANOVA, the table shows that the computed value is 9.19 and the p-value of <0.001 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the mastery of TLE teachers when grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

The result implies that TLE teachers having Bachelor’s Degree as their highest educational attainment have a significantly lower mastery level compared to those have Master’s Degree and Doctorate degree. This further indicates that highest educational attainment of TLE teachers affects their mastery level.

Comparison Between Means of Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment

The table below shows the comparison between means of the mastery of TLE teachers when grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

Table 6.7. *Comparison Between Means of Mastery of TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment*

Comparison	Computed value	p-value	Interpretation
Bachelor's degree vs. Master's degree	-2.27	0.012	Significant
Bachelor's degree vs. Doctorate degree	-5.95	0.002	Significant
Master's degree vs. Doctorate degree	-3.68	0.080	Not significant

As shown in the table, using Scheffe’s test, the computed values of -2.27 and -5.95 with the p-values of 0.012 and 0.002 indicates that there is a significant difference at .05 level of significance when TLE teachers having Bachelor's degree and Master's degree is compared and teachers having Bachelor's degree and Doctorate degree is compared, respectively.

The result of the data above implies that the mastery level of TLE teacher with Doctorate degree is far more comparable to the mastery level of TLE teachers with Bachelor’s degree and Master’s degree. This also means that as the teacher continue to learn and grow professionally, their mastery of the subject matter improve.

This findings was contradicted by the study of Elli and Ricafort (2020) which revealed that the absence of this relationship may be attributed to the varying graduate programs pursued by these teachers. Notably, only 6% of those with master's degree units have specialized in TLE, while most teachers with advanced degrees lack alignment with the subject area. The findings indicate that academic qualifications alone do not determine teaching competency. Observations revealed that some highly qualified teachers, despite having content knowledge, lacked strong communication skills and effective classroom management.

Conversely, newly graduated teachers still completing their degrees were observed to be more competent, demonstrating a balance of content knowledge, pedagogical skills, and professionalism. This highlights the importance of practical teaching abilities over formal educational attainment in ensuring effective teaching.

Difference in the Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Sex

The table below shows the difference in the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when grouped according to their sex.

Table 7.1. *Difference in the Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Sex*

Sex	n	Mean
Male	35	3.22
Female	72	3.02

Computed value (t): 2.49

p-value: 0.724

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that using T-test, the computed value is 2.49 and the p-value of 0.724 is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their sex.

This result implies that the challenges encountered by the TLE teachers are the same when they are grouped according to their sex. The difficulties and obstacles encountered by male and female TLE teachers in their teaching practice are the same. The result reveal that most of their learners respond negatively to their lessons.

The result contrast with the study of Conda and Benavides (2024), highlighting a significant imbalance in the gender distribution among TLE teachers, which points to diversity issues within the field. This suggests a possible gender disparity in career choices within the education sector, with more women choosing TLE teaching roles. The predominance of female TLE teachers can affect the variety of perspectives and role models available to students. It's important for students to have mentors of both genders to provide well-rounded guidance. Additionally, the gender distribution can influence teaching methods and classroom interactions, as different genders may bring unique teaching styles and viewpoints, enriching the learning experience.

Difference in the Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age

The table below shows the difference in the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when grouped according to their age.

Table 7.2. *Difference in the Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age*

Age	n	Mean
30 years old & below	16	3.27
31-40 years old	45	3.05
41-50 years old	36	2.95
51-60 years old	10	3.38

Computed value (F): 4.75

p-value: 0.004

Decision: Reject H_0

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that using ANOVA, the computed value is 4.75 and the p-value of 0.004 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their age.

This result implies that the challenges encountered by the TLE teachers are not the same when they are grouped according to their age. This also means that the age of the TLE teachers has an effect on the challenges they encounter in teaching the subject.

Comparison Between Means of Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age

The table on the next page shows the comparison between means of the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when grouped according to their age.

Table 7.3. *Comparison Between Means of Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age*

Comparison	Computed value	p-value	Interpretation
30 years old & below vs. 31-40 years old	0.21	0.304	Not significant
30 years old & below vs. 51-60 years old	0.32	0.063	Not significant
30 years old & below vs. 41-50 years old	-0.11	0.909	Not significant
31-40 years old vs. 41-50 years old	0.10	0.704	Not significant
31-40 years old vs. 51-60 years old	-0.33	0.120	Not significant
41-50 years old vs. 51-60 years old	-0.43	0.024	Significant

Using Scheffe's test, the table shows that when the mean of the mastery of TLE teachers when those who age 30 years old & below is compared to 31-40 years old, the 30 years old & below and 51-60 years old, the 30 years old & below and 41-50 years old, 31-40 years old and 41-50 years old, and the 31-40 years old and 51-60 years old is compared, the computed values are 0.21, 0.32, -0.11, 0.10, and -0.33 and the p-values are 0.304, 0.063, 0.909, 0.704, and 0.120, respectively. All of the comparison signifies a not significant difference in their means of challenges encountered as TLE teachers. However, there is a significant difference between the means of the

challenges encountered by TLE teachers aging 41-50 years old and aging 51-60 years old with the computed value of -0.43 and a p-value of 0.024.

The result implies that the challenges level of TLE teacher aging 41-50 years old is significantly lower than a 51-60 years old teacher. The result further reveals that older teachers find it difficult to integrate technology in their area of specialization. Many older teachers have honed their teaching skills using traditional methods over many years. Switching to new technological tools can disrupt established routines and practices. There can be a fear of making mistakes or not being able to handle technical issues, leading to a reluctance to experiment with new technologies. A natural resistance to change can be more pronounced among them who have been successful using traditional methods which lead to distrust about the value of incorporating technology into their teaching.

This findings was supported with the study on Profile, Proficiency, and Challenges of Teachers in Integrating ICT in Technology and Livelihood Education by Conda and Benavides (2024) where they argued that teachers may potentially offer a heap of pedagogical experience to the study. The presence of teachers in the 21-25 and 26-30 age groups indicates the inclusion of younger educators. These teachers may bring a fresh perspective and potentially be more tech-savvy, which could impact their approach to ICT integration in TLE. The relatively smaller percentage of teachers aged 36-40 may reflect a potential gap in terms of teaching experience and familiarity with newer educational technologies. Bridging this gap through training and collaboration may be beneficial.

Difference in the Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Length of Service

The table on the next page shows the difference in the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when grouped according to their length of service.

Table 7.4. *Difference in the Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Length of Service*

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1-5 years	12	3.34
6-10 years	25	3.07
11-15 years	34	3.04
16 years and above	36	3.04

Computed value (F): 1.99

p-value: 0.129

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that using ANOVA, the computed value is 1.99 and the p-value of 0.129 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the in the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their length of service.

This result implies that the challenges encountered by the TLE teachers do not differ when they are grouped according to their length of service. This also means that the length of service of the TLE teachers do not have an effect on the challenges they encounter in teaching the subject. It suggests that both novice and experienced teachers face similar difficulties in their roles. These include issues such as resource limitations, student engagement, curriculum changes, and balancing administrative tasks and paper works with teaching responsibilities.

However, previous research of Bingimlas (2019) as cited by Conda and Benavides (2024) contradicts to the finding of this study. According to him, tailoring professional development opportunities to cater to the needs of teachers at different stages of their careers is important. Newer teachers may require more foundational training, while experienced teachers may benefit from advanced courses or leadership development. Schools and educational authorities should consider succession planning to ensure a smooth transition of knowledge and expertise as more experienced teachers approach retirement.

Difference in the Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Marital Status

The table below shows the difference in the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when grouped according to their marital status.

Table 7.5. *Difference in the Challenges encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Marital Status*

<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Single	28	3.13
Married	79	3.07

Computed value (t): 0.68

p-value: 0.984

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table reflects that the mean of challenges encountered by TLE single teachers is 3.13 and the mean of 3.07 is of the TLE married teachers. Using -test, the computed value is 0.68 and the p-value of 0.984 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the challenges of TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their marital status.

This result implies that the challenges encountered by the TLE teachers do not differ when they are grouped according to their marital status. This also means that the marital status of the TLE teachers has no significant effect on the challenges they encounter in teaching the subject. Single and married teachers experience the same level of challenges encountered.

Difference in the Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment

The table below shows the difference in the challenges encountered by TLE teachers when grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

Table 7.6. *Difference in the Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment*

Highest Educational Attainment	n	Mean
Bachelor's degree	49	3.17
Master's degree	52	3.05
Doctorate degree	6	2.61

Computed value (F): 6.06

p-value: 0.003

Decision: Reject H_0

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table above shows that the mean of teachers who have Bachelor's degree is 3.17, those who have a Master's degree have a mean of 3.05 and those who have Doctorate degree have a mean of 2.61 in their challenges as TLE teachers. Using ANOVA, the computed value is 6.06 and the p-value of 0.003 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the in the challenges of TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their highest educational attainment. This result implies that the challenges encountered by the TLE teachers are not the same when they are grouped according to their highest educational attainment. This also means that the highest educational attainment of the TLE teachers has a significant influence on the challenges they encounter in teaching the subject.

Comparison Between Means of Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment

The table below shows the comparison between means of challenges encountered by TLE teachers when grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

Table 7.7. *Comparison Between Means of Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment*

Comparison	Computed value	p-value	Interpretation
Bachelor's degree vs. Master's degree	0.12	0.280	Not significant
Bachelor's degree vs. Doctorate degree	0.56	0.004	Significant
Master's degree vs. Doctorate degree	0.44	0.033	Significant

Using Scheffe's test, the table shows that when the means of the challenges of TLE teachers grouped according to highest educational attainment are compared, between Bachelor's degree and Master's degree, the computed value is 0.12 and the p-value of 0.280 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is no significant difference between the challenges of TLE teachers. However, when the Bachelor's degree and Doctorate degree, and Master's degree and Doctorate degree are compared, the computed values are 0.56 and 0.44 and the p-values are 0.004 and 0.033, respectively. These comparison means that there is a significant difference in their means of challenges encountered as TLE teachers.

The result implies that the challenges of TLE teachers having a Doctorate degree are significantly lower than those who have a Bachelor's degree and Master's degree. The result further reveals that a teacher with Doctorate degree experience a little of challenges compared to those who were Bachelor's degree and Master's degree. This is due to the trainings and ongoing professional development opportunities they have.

The findings of this study was supported with the statement of Conda and Benavides (2024) that the presence of teachers with diverse educational backgrounds suggests that TLE departments may benefit from a mix of perspectives and expertise. Teachers with bachelor's degrees bring subject-specific knowledge, while those with master's degrees can contribute advanced pedagogical insights. Teachers with master's degrees, especially those with CAR master's degrees, may have gone through specialized trainings that can position them as potential leaders or specialists in TLE curriculum development and instructional design. It is essential to offer ongoing professional development opportunities for both groups. Bachelor's degree holders can benefit from training that enhances their pedagogical skills, while master's degree holders can engage in advanced training, research, and curriculum innovation. Teachers with master's degree may have a deeper understanding of educational theories and methodologies, which can positively impact students' learning experiences. Their advanced training can potentially lead to improved student outcomes.

Difference in the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Sex

The table below shows the difference in the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when grouped according to their sex.

Table 8.1. *Difference in the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Male	35	2.52
Female	72	2.71

Computed value (t): -2.10
 p-value: 0.094
 Decision: Accept H_0
 Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

As presented in the table above, male teachers have a mean of 2.52 and female teachers display a mean of 2.71 in the opportunities obtained as TLE teacher. Using T-test, the computed value is -2.10 and the p-value of 0.094 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their sex. This result implies that the opportunities obtained by the TLE teachers do not differ when they are grouped according to their sex. This also means that male and female teachers experienced the same level of opportunities. Male and female TLE teachers have similar access to professional development, career advancement, resources, and other opportunities in their field. Regardless of gender, they were equal access to opportunities which means they have a fair and supportive work environment.

The result of this study support the statement of Conda and benavides (2024) that having a mix of male and female TLE teachers can provide students with a broader range of role models and career options, potentially encouraging more inclusive and diverse career choices. Consideration should be given to tailoring professional development opportunities to address the specific needs and interests of both male and female TLE teachers. For example, providing training in gender-inclusive teaching methods can be valuable. The sex distribution data may also reflect broader societal stereotypes and expectations regarding career choices. Encouraging diversity and breaking down gender-based stereotypes can be a focus in teacher training and curriculum development.

Similarly, the study of Elli and Ricafort (2020) found no significant relationship between gender and the level of competency across the four areas of TLE. This suggests that TLE teachers, regardless of gender, possess comparable levels of competency in teaching these areas. It also implies that both male and female teachers have acquired the necessary knowledge and skills for teaching TLE through equal opportunities provided by the school for professional development. As previously noted, teachers must participate in in-service training sessions during the Learning Action Cell (LAC), which are conducted regularly to enhance their competencies in teaching TLE.

Difference in the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age

The table below shows the difference in the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when grouped according to their age.

Table 8.2. *Difference in the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
30 years old & below	16	2.37
31-40 years old	45	2.64
41-50 years old	36	2.74
51-60 years old	10	2.73

Computed value (F): 3.00
 p-value: 0.034
 Decision: Reject H_0
 Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

As presented in the table, in terms of opportunities obtained by TLE teachers, the 30 years old & below has a mean of 2.37, the 31-40 years old reveal a mean of 2.64, the 41-50 years old has a mean of 2.74, and the 51-60 years old has a mean of 2.73. Using ANOVA, the computed value is 3.00 and the p-value of 0.034 is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their age. This result implies that the opportunities obtained by the TLE teachers differ significantly when they are grouped according to their age. This also means that teachers from different age group experience the different level of opportunities obtained. Younger teachers may have different career development needs and goals compared to older teachers. For example, younger teachers might be seeking more foundational training, while older teachers could be looking for leadership opportunities. Opportunities such as promotions or leadership roles might be more accessible to older teachers due to their years of experience and established track record.

Comparison Between Means of Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age

The table below shows the comparison between means of opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when grouped according to their age.

Using Scheffe's test, the table shows that when the means of the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers are compared according to age, between 30 years old & below and 31-40 years old, 30 years old & below and 41-50 years old, 31-40 years old and 41-50 years old, 31-40 years old and 51-60 years old, and between 41-50 years old and 51-60 years old, the computed values are -0.27, -0.36, -

0.10, -0.09, and 0.01 and the p-values of 0.189, 0.228, 0.775, 0.952, 1.000 are greater than 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is no significant difference between the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers who belong to these group of comparison. However, when the 30 years old & below and 51-60 years old are compared, the computed value is -0.37 and the p-value is 0.042, respectively. This comparison means that there is a significant difference in their means of opportunities obtained.

Table 8.3. *Comparison Between Means of Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Age*

Comparison	Computed value	p-value	Interpretation
30 years old & below vs. 31-40 years old	-0.27	0.189	Not significant
30 years old & below vs. 51-60 years old	-0.37	0.042	Significant
30 years old & below vs. 41-50 years old	-0.36	0.228	Not significant
31-40 years old vs. 41-50 years old	-0.10	0.775	Not significant
31-40 years old vs. 51-60 years old	-0.09	0.952	Not significant
41-50 years old vs. 51-60 years old	0.01	1.000	Not significant

The result implies that the opportunities obtained by TLE teacher aging 30 years old & below is significantly lower than those who are aging 51-60 years old. The result further reveals that a teacher aging 30 years old & below experience a little of opportunities obtained compared to those who were aging 51-60 years old. Older teachers typically have more years of service, which often translates into a deeper understanding of the educational system, institutional culture, and professional networks.

The results align with Ferrer's (2022) study, which indicates that while younger TLE teachers (30 years old and below) bring fresh perspectives and adaptability to new technologies, they often have fewer opportunities compared to their older counterparts aged 51-60 years. This is because younger teachers are generally at the beginning of their careers, focusing on foundational training and gaining experience. Older teachers, with their extensive knowledge and established reputations, often access more advanced professional development opportunities, leadership roles, and specialized positions. This disparity underscores the need for targeted support and professional development programs that address the unique needs of teachers at different career stages, ensuring equitable opportunities for growth and advancement across all age groups.

Difference in the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Length of Service

The table below shows the difference in the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when grouped according to their length of service.

Table 8.4. *Difference in the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Length of Service*

Length of Service	n	Mean
1-5 years	12	2.33
6-10 years	25	2.58
11-15 years	34	2.67
16 years and above	36	2.77

Computed value (F): 3.50

p-value: 0.018

Decision: Reject H_0

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 8.4 shows that above, in terms of opportunities of TLE teachers, those who served for 1-5 years has a mean of 2.33, teachers who served for 6-10 years display a mean of 2.58, those who served for 11-15 years show a mean of 2.67 and those who served for 16 years and above has a mean of 2.77. Using ANOVA, the computed value is 3.50 and the p-value of 0.018 is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the opportunities of TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their length of service.

This result implies that the opportunities of the TLE teachers differ significantly when they are grouped according to their length of service. This also means that teachers with different length of service as TLE teacher have come across to different opportunities.

Comparison Between Means of Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Length of Service

The table below shows the comparison between means of opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when grouped according to their length of service.

Table 8.5. *Comparison Between Means of Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Length of Service*

Comparison	Computed value	p-value	Interpretation
1-5 years vs. 11-15 years	-0.34	0.122	Not significant
1-5 years vs. 6-10 years	-0.26	0.394	Not significant
1-5 years vs. 16 years and above	-0.44	0.024	Significant
11-15 years vs. 6-10 years	0.09	0.891	Not significant
11-15 years vs. 16 years and above	-0.10	0.827	Not significant
6-10 years vs. 16 years and above	-0.18	0.431	Not significant

Using Scheffe's test, the table shows that when the means of the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers are compared according to length of service, between 1-5 year and 11-15 years, between 1-5 years and 6-10 years, the 11-15 years and 6-10 years, 11-15 years and 16 years and above, and 6-10 years and 16 years and above, the computed values are -0.34, -0.26, 0.09, -0.10, and -0.18 and the p-values of 0.122, 0.394, 0.891, 0.827, and 0.431, respectively are greater than 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is no significant difference between the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers who belong to these group of comparison. However, when the 1-5 years and 16 years and above are compared, the computed value is -0.44 and the p-value is 0.024, respectively. This comparison means that there is a significant difference in their means of opportunities obtained.

The result implies that the opportunities obtained by TLE teacher having 1-5 years of service is significantly lower than those who served for 16 years and above. The result further discloses that a teacher who were in the service for a long time met more opportunities than those who were new in the service. This experience can make them more eligible for leadership roles and other opportunities. Also, a longer track record of successful teaching and professional accomplishments can make older teachers more competitive candidates for promotions, awards, and other opportunities.

The findings are supported by Ferrer's study (2022). As teachers gain more years of experience, they become more adept at anticipating classroom challenges and adjusting their strategies to manage these issues effectively. The length of exposure to a specific job or circumstance, along with personal and professional characteristics, greatly influences the success of an educational program. Teachers with more experience in the TLE field have refined their pedagogical approaches and classroom management techniques, which enhances their effectiveness as educators. This accumulated experience not only improves their ability to deliver high-quality instruction but also positions them as valuable mentors to less experienced teachers. Such mentorship and the sharing of best practices contribute to a collaborative and supportive teaching environment, fostering continuous professional growth.

Difference in the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Marital Status

The table below shows the difference in the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when grouped according to their marital status.

Table 8.6. *Difference in the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Marital Status*

<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Single	28	2.47
Married	79	2.71

Computed value (t): -2.47
p-value: 0.944
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 8.6 above shows that in terms of opportunities obtained by TLE teachers those who are single display a mean of 2.47 and those who are married show a mean of 2.71. Using T-test, the computed value is -2.47 and the p-value of 0.944 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their marital status.

This result implies that the opportunities obtained by the TLE teachers are almost the same when they are grouped according to their marital status. This also means that the marital status of TLE teachers do not affect the opportunities offered to them. Professional development opportunities, such as training programs, workshops, and seminars, are equally available to all teachers regardless of their marital status. This ensures that all teachers have the same chances to improve their skills and knowledge. This also implies that schools prioritize merit and performance when offering opportunities for career advancement and professional growth. This means that opportunities are based on a teacher's qualifications, experience, and performance, rather than personal characteristics like marital status.

The study's findings are consistent with Colano's (2024) research, which found no significant differences in the teaching strategies used by TLE teachers who are single, married, or widowed/legally separated. This suggests a notable consistency in their teaching methods, regardless of their marital status, indicating that personal circumstances do not significantly affect their professional practices. This uniformity can be attributed to comprehensive training programs, standardized educational policies, and a shared educational culture within the Division of Valenzuela. Consequently, all TLE teachers have equal opportunities to employ effective teaching strategies, fostering a stable and equitable learning environment for all students.

Difference in the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment

The table below shows the difference in the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

Table 8.7 shows that in terms of opportunities of TLE teachers, those who are Bachelor's degree has a mean of 2.39, the Master's degree earn a mean of 2.84, and the Doctorate degree display a mean of 3.03. Using ANOVA, the computed value is 21.99 and the p-value of <0.001 is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when they are grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

Table 8.7. *Difference in the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment*

Highest Educational Attainment	n	Mean
Bachelor's degree	49	2.39
Master's degree	52	2.84
Doctorate degree	6	3.03

Computed value (F): 21.99

p-value: <0.001

Decision: Reject H_0

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

This result implies that the opportunities obtained by the TLE teachers differ significantly when they are grouped according to their highest educational attainment. This also means that teachers with highest educational attainment have different opportunities obtained. Teachers with higher educational qualifications, such as Master's or Doctorate degrees, tend to have greater access to opportunities. These might include leadership roles, specialized training, research opportunities, and higher chances of promotion.

Comparison Between Means of Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment

The table below shows the comparison between means of opportunities obtained by TLE teachers when grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

Table 8.8. *Comparison Between Means of Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers when grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment*

Comparison	Computed value	p-value	Interpretation
Bachelor's degree vs. Master's degree	-0.45	<0.001	Significant
Bachelor's degree vs. Doctorate degree	-0.64	<0.001	Significant
Master's degree vs. Doctorate degree	-0.19	0.478	Not significant

Using Scheffe's test, the table shows that when the means of the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers are compared according to highest educational attainment, between Bachelor's degree and Master's degree and between Bachelor's degree and Doctorate degree, the computed values are -0.45 and -0.64 and the p-values of both are <0.001, respectively are greater than 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is a significant difference between the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers who belong to these group of comparison. However, when the Master's degree and Doctorate degree are compared, the computed value is -0.19 and the p-value is 0.478. This comparison means that there is no significant difference in their means of opportunities obtained.

The result implies that the opportunities obtained by TLE teacher having a Bachelor's degree is significantly lower than those who Master's degree and Doctorate degree. Advanced degrees often come with additional skills and knowledge that can make teachers more competitive for various opportunities. Highly educated teachers are frequently involved in mentorship roles, guiding and supporting their colleagues.

According to Ferrer (2022) level of educational attainment significantly influences the professional opportunities available to TLE teachers. Those holding only a Bachelor's degree may find their career advancement somewhat limited compared to their peers with advanced degrees. Teachers with MA/MS units or degrees often have access to more advanced professional development opportunities, leadership roles, and specialized teaching positions. For instance, they might be eligible for roles that involve curriculum development, research projects, or administrative responsibilities within their schools. On the other hand, teachers with higher educational qualifications, such as Ph.D./Ed.D. units, although fewer in number, have the potential to pursue even more specialized roles, including higher education teaching positions, consultancy roles, or positions that influence educational policy and practice at broader levels.

Relationship between the Mastery of TLE Teachers and Performance

The table below shows the relationship between the mastery of TLE teachers and performance.

Table 9. *Relationship between the Mastery of TLE Teachers and Performance*

Variables	n	Mean
Mastery of TLE teachers	107	20.82
Teacher's performance	107	4.57

Computed value (r): 0.19

p-value: 0.045

Decision: Reject H_0

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

As shown in Table 9, the mastery of TLE teachers has a mean of 20.82 while the mean of teacher's performance is 4.57. Using the Pearson r, the computed value (r) is 0.19 with a P-value of 0.045. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between the mastery of TLE teachers and performance.

This implies that mastery of TLE teachers is significantly related to their performance. It also means that the level of a teacher's

expertise and knowledge in the subject matter has a measurable impact on their teaching effectiveness and overall performance. Teachers who have a high level of mastery in TLE are likely to perform better in their teaching roles. This includes delivering more effective lessons, engaging students more successfully, and achieving better student outcomes. Teachers with a strong grasp of the subject matter can provide clearer explanations, relate concepts to real-world applications, and address student questions more effectively.

The result of this study is in consonance with the findings of Villegas (2022) when he discovered that TLE teachers' competencies in instructional skills, classroom management, guidance, and personal and professional abilities are closely linked to students' work skills and attitudes towards work. This indicates that the way teachers manage their classes can significantly impact student success. Given that students respond to lessons in varied ways, it is crucial for teachers to continually assess their teaching capabilities, including subject expertise, attendance, teaching methodologies, and overall attitude. The research also underscores the correlation between effective teaching and student achievement, highlighting the necessity for teachers to improve their teaching proficiency to provide high-quality education. Furthermore, the study points out that teachers have a substantial influence on students' attitudes. It stresses the importance of fostering a supportive learning environment to encourage student motivation and engagement. Additionally, the findings suggest that students' academic confidence and motivation are enhanced when they perceive their teachers as caring. When teachers show genuine interest and understanding towards their students, it positively affects students' participation and effort in their learning.

The finding of this study is also supported by the study of Basal (2022). It was found that TLE teachers rated their instructional competencies as "Competent" across several areas: subject matter mastery, pedagogical skills, and classroom management. Specifically, teachers rated their mastery of the subject matter with a grand mean of 4.09, indicating a strong knowledge and skill base that helps achieve educational objectives and engages students. In terms of pedagogical skills, teachers scored a grand mean of 4.05, reflecting their ability to effectively organize and present lessons using varied instructional strategies to enhance student understanding. Classroom management skills received a grand mean of 4.17, showing that teachers are adept at creating structured and conducive learning environments, minimizing distractions, and promoting positive behavior. This competency ensures student safety and supports a productive learning atmosphere.

Relationship between the Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers and Performance

The table below shows the relationship between the challenges encountered by TLE teachers and performance.

Table 10. *Relationship between the Challenges Encountered by TLE Teachers and Performance*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Challenges encountered by TLE teachers	107	3.08
Teacher's performance	107	4.57

Computed value (r): -0.27
p-value: 0.005
Decision: Reject Ho
Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that the challenges encountered by TLE teachers display a mean of 3.08 and the teacher's performance has a mean of 4.57. Using Pearson r , it reveals that the computed value obtained is -0.27 , while the p -value is 0.005 . The p -value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between the level of challenges encountered and the level of performance of TLE teachers.

The result implies that the challenges encountered by TLE teachers have a significant relationship to their teaching performance. The more they have the opportunity to access resources that could aid in enhancing their teaching techniques, the more they can perform their duties as teachers. With the number of opportunity they have to enhance their teaching techniques or addressing obstacles in their professional roles, the more they can execute and carry out what is expected from them.

The finding is in agreement with the study of Barcelona et al. (2023) which highlighted a significant concern beyond the insufficient resources and facilities in teaching TLE: the waning enthusiasm among many students. The deficiency in laboratory equipment poses a serious threat to students' interest in TLE subjects, particularly in areas like cookery, prompting some to consider switching their academic focus. The decline in students' engagement with their studies may stem from various factors, including the lack of laboratory resources, the teacher's effectiveness in the classroom, and the financial circumstances of students.

Thus, it is imperative for educators to dedicate themselves to delivering hands-on learning experiences. Additionally, educational institutions should prioritize investments in well-equipped laboratories to enrich students' practical learning and skills, ultimately reigniting their interest in the field.

In the Division of Davao del Norte, it was observed that TLE teachers encountered several challenges in developing their pedagogical content knowledge. One common issue was the limited availability of specialized professional development programs that integrated both technical expertise and effective teaching strategies. Additionally, the dynamic nature of vocational subjects posed difficulties for TLE teachers in adapting instructional approaches to align with industry changes, potentially impacting their ability to provide students with relevant and up-to-date knowledge and skills.

Relationship between the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers and Performance

The table below shows the relationship between the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers and their performance.

Table 11. *Relationship between the Opportunities Obtained by TLE Teachers and Performance*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Opportunities of TLE teachers	107	2.65
Teacher's performance	107	4.57

Computed value (r): 0.25

p-value: 0.008

Decision: Reject Ho

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

As shown in Table 30, the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers garner a mean of 2.65 and their teaching performance shows a mean of 4.57. Using the Pearson r , the computed value (G) is 0.25 with a P-value of 0.008. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and this means that there is a significant relationship between opportunities obtained by TLE teachers and their performance. This implies that the opportunities obtained by TLE teachers is significantly related to their performance. When they have the opportunities to excel in their field, they continue to strive to render the best in teaching and delivering their duty at their best.

This finding agree to the study carried out by Pardjono et al. (2018) highlighted the importance of schools partnering with industries to blend learning with real-world work experiences. They suggested creating a structured collaboration framework for this purpose. In vocational education, such partnerships aim to equip students with various skills needed for employment, with information technology skills being particularly important. For effective teaching and learning, it is vital for teachers to have technical support, including access to software and hardware services. This enables educators to fully utilize Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in vocational education. The results conform to Barcelona et al. (2023) findings which suggested that TLE teachers acknowledge vocational training as a valuable avenue for refining their instructional approaches and broadening their skill set. By actively participating in vocational training programs, they not only stay abreast of evolving industry practices but also acquire new skills that can enrich their teaching methodologies. This continuous professional development empowers TLE teachers to provide students with relevant and up-to-date knowledge, thereby enhancing their preparedness for future employment opportunities. Research suggests that TLE teachers who engage in vocational training exhibit a positive correlation with improved student academic performance, as they are better equipped to deliver practical, industry-relevant instruction that resonates with learners.

Conclusions

Based from the findings above, the researcher therefore concludes that:

Majority of the respondents were female, aged between 31- 40 years old, served for 11-15 years, married, and with Master's degree.

The respondents possess average knowledge in the subject TLE.

The TLE teachers have a moderate level of difficulties and obstacles encountered in their teaching practice. They do not have enough resources to deliver the lesson well and some of them lack expertise in the subject they taught.

The TLE teachers have a low opportunity to enhance their teaching techniques or addressing obstacles in their professional roles. They lack opportunity to attend international trainings and/or seminars, invited as resource speaker to share their knowledge and skills in their area of specialization, and receive/avail scholarship programs in Masteral/PhD.

The TLE teachers have excellent teaching performance in all areas of responsibility.

The mastery level of TLE teachers vary when they are grouped according to their age and highest educational attainment. It showed that the mastery level of the younger TLE teachers is lower than the older ones and the mastery level of TLE teacher with Doctorate degree is comparatively higher than those who were in the Bachelor's and Master's degree.

The challenges encountered by TLE teachers differ when they are grouped according to their age and highest educational attainment. Older TLE teachers encountered greater challenges than the younger ones while teachers having a Doctorate degree experiences lower challenges than those who have a Bachelor's degree and Master's degree.

The opportunities obtained by TLE teachers are influenced by their age, length of service, and highest educational attainment.

The mastery of TLE teachers is significantly related to their performance.

The challenges encountered by TLE teachers significantly impact their teaching performance.

As the opportunities for TLE teachers increase, their performance also increase.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

School administrators can provide interventions like in-service training, creating instructional materials, and developing digital learning

strategies can address weaknesses and improve the competency of TLE teachers.

School administrators can enhance resource allocation to ensure that TLE teachers have access to adequate teaching materials, equipment, and resources to effectively deliver their lessons. They can also offer training sessions focused on effective classroom management, innovative teaching strategies, and the integration of technology in teaching. They are encouraged to promote collaboration among TLE teachers to share resources, ideas, and strategies for overcoming common challenges. TLE teachers can relate lessons to real-world scenarios and everyday life to increase student's interest in the subject.

Education Program Specialist can organize regular workshops and training sessions to enhance TLE teachers' skills and knowledge. Topics can include new teaching methodologies, technology integration, and current trends in vocational education. They may facilitate networking events where TLE teachers can connect, share ideas, and collaborate on projects. This helps build a supportive community and encourages the exchange of best practices. Grants and funding opportunities can also be offered for TLE teachers to conduct research and develop innovative teaching practices.

Education Program Specialist can provide opportunities for professional growth of TLE teachers, such as workshops, conferences, and collaboration, can enhance their teaching skills and, consequently, their performance. Despite challenges, TLE teachers recognize vocational training as an opportunity to enhance their teaching. Participating in professional development programs can positively impact their performance.

TLE teachers who are still young can seek mentors within the field who can provide guidance, share insights, and offer support. They can also collaborate with peers to share resources, ideas, and teaching strategies. They may also consider enrolling in a Master's degree program or professional certifications related to TLE or education to enhance their expertise.

Young and Bachelor's degree holder TLE teachers can work closely with other experienced TLE teachers to share resources, lesson plans, and teaching strategies. They can also maintain a positive attitude and enthusiasm for teaching to inspire and motivate students to learn.

Young and less experienced TLE teachers can consider enrolling in advanced degree programs or obtaining specialized certifications related to TLE to enhance their qualifications and open up new career opportunities. They may regularly read industry publications, attend workshops, and participate in webinars to stay informed about the latest trends and developments in TLE and education. They may join professional organizations and networks related to TLE and education.

TLE teachers are encouraged to stay updated with the latest developments in TLE by attending workshops, seminars, and conferences which can improve their teaching performance.

Education program specialist may provide continuous professional development to TLE teachers through workshops, seminars, and courses. Focus on areas that address their specific challenges, such as classroom management, new teaching technologies, or industry trends. They can also propose a capability building program to improve TLE teacher's mastery of the subject matter, integrate technology effectively in the teaching practices, and address specific challenges they encounter in their teaching roles.

School administrators can provide financial support or incentives for TLE teachers to pursue advanced degrees or certifications. This could include tuition reimbursement, scholarships, or time off for study. They can also implement a system to recognize and reward outstanding TLE teachers.

Future researchers can utilize both qualitative and quantitative research methods to gain a holistic understanding of the challenges and opportunities faced by TLE teachers. Surveys, interviews, and case studies can provide rich, detailed data.

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